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Preparation and magnetoresistance behavior of nickel nanoparticles embedded in hydrogenated carbon film.

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Abstract

Nickel nanoparticles arrays, growth into hydrogenated amorphous carbon, were prepared by means of RF-plasma enhanced chemical vapor deposition and RF-sputtering co-deposition from acetylene and a nickel target. The resulting nanocomposite films were characterized by X-ray diffraction and atomic force microscopy, and their magnetic responses and magnetoresistance behavior were investigated as a function of the exciting magnetic field and the Ni nanoparticles content, which was conveniently controlled by adjusting the deposition time. These physical properties were explained by a combination of hopping and tunneling effects.